

Curtin University

Faculty of Humanities

Coordinated Response to the Policy Review of the National Competitive Grants Program

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This submission represents the collective response of the Faculty of Humanities at Curtin University to the Discussion Paper: A New Plan for ARC-Funded Research. It draws on the perspectives and expertise of researchers with substantial experience in Australian Research Council funding processes, both as applicants and assessors.

The response has been developed by a dedicated working group comprising:

- Associate Professor Robert Briggs
- Professor Katie Ellis (Working Group Chair)
- Associate Professor Tod Jones
- Professor Tama Leaver
- Professor Kit Messham-Muir
- Dr. Giles Thomson
- John Curtin Distinguished Professor David Treagust

This working group was coordinated by the Humanities Dean of Research, Professor Lucy Montgomery, and the Faculty Research Development Advisor, Dr Melanie McKee. It brings together academics who currently hold, or have previously held, ARC funding, and represents researchers at all stages of their career - from Early Career Researchers through to Senior Career Researchers. Their perspectives are informed by direct engagement with ARC processes, recent experiences with grant applications and management, and a deep understanding of the contemporary research environment within Australian universities.

The Working Group met specifically to discuss the NCGP Discussion Paper and formulate a strategic, well-informed submission that reflects the concerns and aspirations of humanities researchers. Their insights have been particularly valuable in identifying potential unintended consequences of the proposed changes and in suggesting modifications that would better serve the research community.

We acknowledge the time, expertise, and commitment contributed by all Working Group members in crafting this response.

The group framed their responses around six key questions as follows:

1. Does the proposed model provide a strong and clear basis for the NCGP over the next 20 years?

The proposed model's aim to simplify and streamline the grant application process is commendable and reflects a genuine effort to reform a complex system. However, it does not provide a sufficiently clear basis for the NCGP over the next 20 years. The changes are so

extensive that it's difficult to comprehend their full implications. What is being proposed appears to be a complete transformation rather than a modification of the existing program.

The model lacks clarity about how it will operate within the current university research environment, where research time and resources are increasingly constrained. It fails to acknowledge trends in university research workloads and the pressures researchers face. There's a disconnect between how universities view ARC grants (increasingly as a cost burden) and how the discussion paper presents research funding opportunities.

While the emphasis on reducing paperwork is timely and necessary given the enormous administrative burden of current ARC grants, the overall vision for supporting research capacity development remains unclear. The model should be considered in the context of the National University Accord, which highlighted that research is not fully funded in Australia. Without addressing this fundamental issue, it's difficult to see how the new model can provide a strong foundation for the next two decades.

2. Does the proposed model adequately address your concerns or those expressed in the initial consultations?

The proposed elimination of artificial distinctions between basic and applied research is a positive step that acknowledges the reality of how research actually functions. However, the model inadequately addresses several key concerns:

Regarding research workforce development, the proposal claims to build research capacity, but provides little concrete explanation of how this will be achieved. The pathways for researchers to establish themselves as independent scholars are unclear, particularly with the removal of dedicated early career research schemes.

The new schemes remove fully funded standalone researcher-focused programs like DECRA, Future Fellowship, and Laureate schemes, replacing them with embedded fellowships across grant categories. For faculties that view research primarily as a cost, this will make securing research support increasingly difficult as there is a clear presumption that most research salary costs will be borne by the university rather than the ARC. The short-term fellowships might distribute opportunities more widely, but the reduction in grants supporting researchers' salaries will likely reduce humanities research capacity. This contradicts the principle of supporting the full cost of research that other major grant schemes often embrace.

For senior researchers, the model appears to reduce opportunities, with no equivalent to the laureate fellowships and limited avenues for securing salary support for chief investigators. The collaborative and prioritize schemes, which might be suitable for senior researchers, are only expected to run every two years, further limiting opportunities.

One potential improvement is the relaxation of partner contribution requirements in certain schemes. This could reduce the difficulties researchers face when working with partners, particularly those from sectors with limited financial resources.

3. Do you foresee any unintended consequences or significant risks which have not been accounted for in the proposed model?

The increased focus on supporting high-risk, high-reward research is a welcome development that could lead to more innovative outcomes. Nevertheless, several significant risks and unintended consequences are apparent:

Loss of early career research independence: The shift from dedicated early career fellowships to embedded positions risks reducing independence for emerging researchers. Current schemes like DECRA provide substantial research time (around 80%) with limited other obligations. Embedded fellowships may create dependency relationships where early career researchers are subject to the priorities and goodwill of senior researchers rather than developing their own research agendas.

Increased administrative burden: Despite claims of streamlining, the model may actually increase administrative load. The emphasis on shorter projects could lead to researchers constantly preparing applications rather than conducting research. The model may encourage a "scattergun" approach of submitting multiple expressions of interest in hopes of securing funding.

Timeline challenges: With two-year project timeframes in some schemes, existing administrative delays in contract finalization could consume a significant portion of the actual research period.

Assessment complications: Without comprehensive assessor education and clear guidelines, evaluators will struggle to adapt to the new framework and may default to applying old scheme criteria inappropriately.

Funding concentration risks: The new structure could potentially concentrate funding among established research centres or institutions, particularly those in certain geographic regions, rather than distributing opportunities equitably.

Geographic disadvantage: The "Prioritise" grants, which represent the largest funding category in the new schema, are capped at \$6 million compared to current Centres of Excellence caps of \$30-35 million. This significant reduction may discourage nationwide collaboration teams that currently often include Western Australian universities. With smaller budgets, teams may focus on East Coast collaborations to reduce the higher costs associated with including WA partners in face-to-face interactions. The new schemes contain no apparent mechanism to ensure WA remains at least as well represented as currently.

Narrowing research diversity: Research not aligned with existing teaching programs might be disadvantaged, limiting exploration in emerging or specialized fields that don't fit neatly into current educational offerings.

4. What issues would need to be addressed in the transition from the current NCGP schemes to the new model?

The scale-based approach to organizing grant schemes offers a refreshing alternative to the traditional discovery/linkage divide and could better accommodate diverse research needs. However, the transition to the new model would require addressing several critical issues:

A clear mapping process between current and proposed schemes is essential. It would be valuable to analyse recent successful grants at various institutions to determine how they would be categorized under the new system. This would help identify any gaps or misalignments in the transition.

A long implementation timeline is crucial, particularly for early career researchers. Configuring a career to be competitive for schemes like DECRA has been a 3-5 year process for many. The transition to any new scheme should be careful not to suddenly change evaluation criteria and disadvantage ECRs (and Future Fellows) who have invested considerable preparation to be competitive in schemes that will no longer exist.

Comprehensive assessor education must be developed and implemented. Without proper guidance, assessors will struggle to evaluate proposals under the new framework, potentially reverting to familiar but no longer applicable criteria from the previous system.

The fellowship transition requires particular attention. The operational details of embedded fellowships remain unclear, including whether researchers apply for them separately or as part of larger project applications, and how the selection process would work. The relationship between applicants, host projects, and fellowship opportunities needs clarification.

5. Are there any features that you would add to, or remove from, the model?

The strengthened support for indigenous research capabilities demonstrates a valuable commitment to a more inclusive research ecosystem. Building on this positive direction, several modifications would further strengthen the proposed model:

Retain independent fellowships: While embedded fellowships may have merit, they should complement rather than replace existing independent fellowship opportunities like DECRA, Future Fellowships, and Laureates. These established programs provide crucial pathways for developing independent research careers and fostering innovative ideas.

Increase overall funding: The fundamental issue of research underfunding in Australia needs addressing. Restructuring the existing funding pool without enlarging it will not resolve the underlying challenges facing the research sector.

Clarify industry and end-user definitions: The model's focus on industry engagement requires a more nuanced definition of "industry" that acknowledges diverse partnership contexts. For researchers working in humanities, "industry" might encompass community organizations, human rights commissions, and not-for-profits, whose engagement models differ from commercial industry partners.

Geographic equity mechanisms: Introduce specific mechanisms to ensure equitable geographic distribution of funding, particularly addressing the challenges faced by WA-based researchers in forming and maintaining collaborative networks with East Coast institutions.

Increase "Prioritise" funding caps: Consider raising the maximum funding available for "Prioritise" grants to a level that better supports true national collaboration, closer to the current Centre of Excellence levels. The current proposed cap of \$6 million (compared to \$30-35 million for Centres of Excellence) will likely discourage nationwide collaborative teams.

6. Do you have any feedback on the proposed grant schemes and their likely effectiveness?

The proposed incorporation of infrastructure support across all grant schemes rather than through separate funding mechanisms is an innovative approach that could better integrate equipment and facilities with research needs. Regarding specific schemes:

Initiate Scheme: The two-year maximum timeframe appears insufficient for substantive research development, particularly when accounting for administrative delays. It's unclear whether this scheme adequately replaces the DECRA's role in supporting high-risk, high-reward research by early career researchers.

Breakthrough Scheme: This scheme may become disproportionately popular as it offers longer timeframes and higher funding levels with relatively modest partnership requirements. It appears well-positioned for researchers transitioning from smaller projects to more substantial collaborations.

Leader & Mentor Scheme: The funding cap of \$250,000 seems inadequate compared to other schemes offering \$500,000-\$600,000. If primarily focused on HDR and postdoctoral mentoring, the scheme may not sufficiently replace other leadership and excellence programs.

Indigenous Capability Scheme: Questions exist about whether the allocation of 30+ grants is aligned with current capacity in this area. Clarification is needed regarding whether this specifically targets indigenous researchers across all fields or is limited to indigenous research topics.

Prioritise Scheme: The significant reduction in funding caps compared to current Centres of Excellence (from \$30-35 million to \$6 million) risks undermining national collaboration networks, particularly for geographically distant institutions like those in Western Australia. This may lead to more regionally concentrated research teams rather than truly national collaborations.

Overall Distribution: The proposed distribution of grants across schemes appears imbalanced, with heavy weighting toward initiate grants and relatively few in larger collaborative categories. This distribution may not optimally support research progression and development.

One positive aspect is the model's potential flexibility. Opening multiple pathways for different types of grants and reducing rigid boundaries between schemes could benefit researchers whose work doesn't fit neatly into current categories. The reduction in administrative paperwork, if actually achieved, would allow researchers to dedicate more time to conducting research rather than managing grant processes. The relaxation of partner contribution requirements in some schemes would also make collaboration more feasible across diverse sectors.

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